

Characterization of household-consumption load profiles in the time and frequency domain

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ABSTRACT

Smart meter (SM) deployment in the residential context provides a vast amount of data that allows diagnose the behavior of household inhabitants. However, the conventional methods to analyze household-consumption load profiles based on time-series techniques, such as Fourier and Wavelet transform, have problems with nonlinear and nonstationary processes. This paper presents a methodology to perform a comprehensive analysis of consumption load profile features based on the detection of oscillation modes in the time–frequency domain for off-line systems. The methodology is based on the Hilbert–Huang transform (HHT) that evaluates the instantaneous frequency (IF) using the empirical mode decomposition (EMD) and some of the variants of this standard technique such as ensemble empirical mode decomposition (EEMD) and complete ensemble empirical mode decomposition with adaptive noise (CEEMDAN). The study presented in this paper compares the accuracy of different techniques by conducting a case study of two households in Spain. Nonetheless, there is a trade-off between the computational burden and accuracy. Furthermore, the methodology reveals the importance of the data sampling frequency (temporal data granularity) for accurate characterization of the load profile. Some household loads produced oscillation modes that became increasingly ill-suited for resolutions of 1 min or higher.

1. Introduction

Energy consumption in the residential sector has been increasing in recent years, and the trend will continue, even more so with the appearance of COVID-19 [1]. It is important to implement and develop on-line and off-line systems that can assess the power fluctuations, related to the power absorbed by the numerous loads of each user [2,3]. The acquisition and analysis of variables in power systems is increasingly complex due to the massive use of nonlinear loads and electronic-based equipment in the residential, commercial, and industrial context [4]. The complexity depends on the characteristics of the electrical signals of the modern equipment, which are related to the different loads (static-, rotating-, and power electronics-based loads) and generators (deterministic-based, stochastic-based) [5].

The increasing popularity of smart meters (SMs) provides an excellent opportunity to monitor and characterize the features of household-consumption load profile [6,7]. The rapid development of advanced metering infrastructure has also increased access to information and the need to explore different algorithms for the analysis of large volumes

of data [8]. The deployment of SMs and the progress of the Internet of Things (IoT) technology has greatly lowered the cost of data acquisition systems, which has permitted a large increase in the number of studies collecting and analyzing large-scale data. Particularly in the residential context, these studies have been conducted at a low data sampling frequency (i.e., high temporal data granularity) [4,9].

The choice of a temporal data granularity for specifying consumption load profile features has a crucial impact on the results of any action or assessment, as discussed in the literature: (i) to dynamically adjust tariff electrics [10,11]; (ii) to improve energy efficiency and comfort in households [12–15]; (iii) to recognize activities (i.e., analysis of energy consumption through observation) [13,16]; (iv) to optimally size renewable generation and storage systems [10,17]; (v) to forecast household load profiles [13,16–18]; (vi) to characterize household consumption load profile features [19,20]; and (vii) to perform load forecasting by applying probabilistic techniques [18].

High data granularity naturally implies larger amounts of data to be locally stored (either hard disk or memory card) or uploaded to

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Nomenclature

$\hat{c}_{i1}(t)$	Signal decomposition with EMD (intrinsic mode functions)
$\hat{c}_i(t)$	Signal decomposition with CEEMDAN (IMF)
$\hat{n}_i(t)$	Gaussian white noise
$\hat{r}_i(t)$	Residual mode
$\hat{x}_i(t)$	$x(t)$ modified with Gaussian white noise
$\theta_i(t)$	Instantaneous phase
$a_i(t)$	Amplitude of each IMF
$E_j(\cdot)$	Decomposition Gaussian white noise
$f_i(t)$	Instantaneous frequency
$H_i(f, t)$	Hilbert Spectrum
L	Total number of IMFs with CEEMDAN
N	Total number of IMFs with EMD
$x(t)$	Household power signal
$X^{new_1}(t)$	Construct signal with CEEMDAN
CEEMDAN	Complete Ensemble Empirical Mode Decomposition with Adaptive Noise
EEMD	Ensemble Empirical Mode Decomposition
EMD	Empirical Mode Decomposition
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
HHT	Hilbert–Huang Transform
HT	Hilbert Transform
IF	Instantaneous Frequency
IMF	Intrinsic Mode Functions
MSE	Mean Squared Error
SM	Smart Meter
STFT	Short time Fourier Transform
WT	Wavelet Transform
WVT	Wigner–Ville Transform

the cloud and make a complex analysis. This has led many researchers to develop analytical tools that could help to segment and cluster SM big data so that it can be analyzed [21,22]. These algorithms are usually time consuming, and thus, the gathered data is not available in real time but as off-line systems. Furthermore, high granularity requires a large bandwidth, which is not always available in individual households.

To date, the major obstacle to accurately describing the features of household-consumption load profiles is the fact that this type of information has not been sampled at a low temporal resolution (high data sampling frequency) that gathers its intrinsic dynamics. The consumption profile is known to fluctuate at a high temporal resolution (i.e., an interval of 0.01–4 Hz) [19]. Current supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) systems can sample consumption data at a higher frequency (typically 1 Hz) although the standard practice is to store averaged values of 1 min or higher.

Some of the main challenges when analyzing load profile features are the detection of associated oscillation modes and how the data sampling period can impact the study of associated frequencies. This last factor is more evident in modern load profiles because consumers have different electrical appliances [19,23,24]. The notion of instantaneous frequency (IF) has also begun to be used for this purpose [25].

The most common methods used to analyze time-series from household-consumption load profiles are statistical analysis, fast Fourier transform (FFT), short time Fourier transform (STFT), Wavelet transform (WT), and Wigner–Ville transform (WVT). All of them have their inherent limitation of time or frequency resolutions [26–31]. These techniques have been used with excellent results in areas such

as medicine and telecommunications and recently have begun to be used in energy systems. Depending on customer-demand load profiles, each approach has its own strengths and weaknesses [32]. On the other hand, the Hilbert–Huang transform (HHT) has gained increasing popularity for frequency analysis and is an alternative for analyzing nonlinear and nonstationary signals in this field [33,34]. The HHT was created initially to study ocean waves, which are non-stationary and non-linear in nature, but over time its application has been spread to other fields. The HHT consists of the empirical mode decomposition (EMD) and Hilbert spectral analysis [35].

Time–frequency analysis disaggregates a signal in both time and frequency domain and is an important supporting technique for building an energy analysis, such as noise cancellation in data-driven building of load forecasting [36]. Current methods to obtain such information, e.g., surveys, are usually costly and time-consuming [37].

The methodology proposed in this paper for off-line systems is based on the HHT to calculate the IF using the EMD. The HHT has some problems related with the mode mixing problem. For this reason, we proposed in this paper the modification of the classic HHT using not only EMD but also ensemble empirical mode decomposition (EEMD) and complete ensemble empirical mode decomposition with adaptive noise (CEEMDAN). A case study of two households in Spain, for a full day using off-line active power data, provided valuable insights when describing the features of consumption load profiles with HHT under different techniques. Furthermore, the methodology revealed the influence of the data sampling frequency (temporal data granularity) for accurate characterization of the load profile. The data set selected throughout one day had different consumption features, namely varying characteristics in terms of the relation between the peak and base load and load fluctuations, which made it possible to take the heterogeneity of real-world load profiles into account. We acknowledge that conducting our analysis with a data sample from two households is a limitation of this study. However, this data sample was adequate to achieve our primary objective of demonstrating the usefulness of the methodology proposed.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the method and techniques used for the decomposition of the signals and introduces the concept of IF. Section 3 shows the results of the decomposition that reflect the features of the consumption load profile by identifying the oscillation modes. Additionally, this section highlights the influence of data sampling frequency (temporal data granularity) for describing the profile features. Finally, Section 4 presents the conclusions that can be derived from this research.

2. Methodology

This section presents a description of the methods used for the decomposition of the signals from the SM data. The objective is to describe the algorithms for the EMD, EEMD, and CEEMDAN techniques and the concept of IF, which is used to identify different modes of oscillation. In this section, the reader can also find a comparative theoretical analysis of the methods used. This provides a clear idea of the advantages and disadvantages of each.

The arrival of new technologies to modern power systems has increased the complexity of the network and also the need of new methodologies for analyzing signals that have nonlinear or both non-stationary properties. For many years, Fourier-based analyses were enough for this purpose because it was not necessary to use the concept of instantaneous frequency (IF).

2.1. Fast Fourier Transform (FFT)

The FFT is an approach that allows the extraction of frequency information from time-series data. FFT is an algorithm to understand the behavior of data in the frequency domain. The FFT is based on the

calculation of discrete Fourier Transform much faster than other methods. FFT properties cause some undesirable characteristics in spectrum analysis like aliasing and leakage. Because of the many calculations involved in transforming, the process has some problems related to the computational time. The FFT has some difficulties in the detection of low frequencies, and the resolution time–frequency is not the best.

2.2. Hilbert Huang Transform (HHT)

The combination of the EMD technique and Hilbert spectral analysis gave rise to the HHT. The HHT uses the adaptive time–frequency property of the EMD and the good resolution of the HT when the signal is linear and stationary. The HHT is very useful for extracting information from noisy nonlinear or nonstationary data. The applications of this technique to the signal analysis of power systems have increased and are now common to find in some publications that use EMD to identify perturbations, harmonics, and other behaviors in modern grids. This paper proposes a modification in the classic HHT using not only EMD but also EEMD and CEEMDAN techniques.

2.2.1. Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD)

EMD has been proposed as an adaptive time–frequency data analysis method [38]. EMD does not require any restrictive assumption on the underlying model of the process or system under analysis, and it is able to handle both nonlinear and nonstationary signals. However, the algorithm has some limitations in identifying closely spaced spectral tones and components appearing intermittently in the signal. The aim of the EMD method is to decompose a nonlinear and nonstationary signal $x(t)$ into a sum of intrinsic mode functions (IMFs) that satisfies two conditions [39]:

1. Symmetric upper or lower envelopes (zero mean).
2. The numbers of zero-crossing and extrema that are either equal or differ by exactly one.

EMD has been adjusted to reduce the mode mixing phenomenon and thus ensures a better identification of the different frequencies that can appear in a process or system [25,40]. In summary, HHT takes the result obtained from EMD and applies the Hilbert transform (HT) to each IMF in order to calculate the IF and visualize the Hilbert spectrum.

2.2.2. Ensemble Empirical Mode Decomposition (EEMD)

The HHT was created initially to study ocean waves, which are nonstationary and nonlinear, but over time its application has spread to other fields. The HHT is constituted by EMD and Hilbert spectral analysis [38,41]. Wu and Huang proposed a variation of the EMD by presenting a noise-assisted data analysis (NADA). This variation was coined the EEMD and defines the true IMF components as the mean of an ensemble of trials, each consisting of the signal plus a white noise of finite amplitude [42]. EEMD is described as follows:

1. Add a white noise series to the data base $x(t)$.
2. Decompose the data with added white noise using EMD to obtain the IMFs.
3. Repeat step 1 and step 2 again, but with different white noise series each time.
4. Obtain the (ensemble) means of the corresponding IMFs of the decompositions as the final result.

The main effect of the decomposition using EEMD is that the added white noise series cancel each other in the final mean of the corresponding IMFs.

The main goal of applying the HHT is to have a tool to manage the time–frequency–energy paradigm of data. One way to express the nonstationary is to find the instantaneous frequency and amplitude. This was the reason why Hilbert spectral analysis was included as a part of the HHT. The spectral analysis is a powerful tool to analyze the statistical characteristics of stochastic data [43]. A Hilbert spectrum is

a 3D representation of the instantaneous amplitude and frequency as a function of time for each IMF.

The Hilbert spectrum is defined as:

$$H_i(f, t) \triangleq \begin{cases} a_i(t) & \text{for } f = f_i(t) \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

For a general multi component signal, the Hilbert spectrum is defined as the sum of Hilbert spectra of all the IMFs, as given in:

$$H(f, t) \triangleq \sum_{i=1}^N H_i(f, t), \quad (2)$$

where N is the total number of IMFs.

2.2.3. Complete Ensemble Empirical Mode Decomposition with Adaptive Noise (CEEMDAN)

The CEEMDAN, an improved algorithm of EMD and EEMD, can adaptively decompose complex signals into IMFs in order. The specific steps of the CEEMDAN are summarized by the following algorithm [44]:

1. Add Gaussian white noise $\hat{n}_i(t)$ to the target signal $x(t)$:

$$\hat{x}_i(t) = x(t) + \hat{n}_i(t), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N \quad (3)$$

2. Decompose $\hat{x}_i(t)$ by EMD to obtain the first IMF $\hat{c}_{i1}(t)$ and residual mode $\hat{r}_i(t)$:

$$\hat{x}_i(t) = \hat{c}_{i1}(t) + \hat{r}_i(t), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N. \quad (4)$$

3. Obtain the first IMF of CEEMDAN by calculating the mean of $\hat{c}_{i1}(t)$:

$$\hat{c}_i(t) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \hat{c}_{i1}(t) \quad (5)$$

4. Obtain the residue $\hat{r}_1(t) = x(t) - \hat{c}_1(t)$.

5. Decompose Gaussian white noise $\hat{n}_i(t)$ by EMD:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \hat{n}_1(t) \\ \hat{n}_2(t) \\ \vdots \\ \hat{n}_N(t) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \hat{c}_{n_{11}}(t) & \dots & \hat{c}_{n_{1j}}(t) & \hat{r}_{n_1}(t) \\ \hat{c}_{n_{21}}(t) & \dots & \hat{c}_{n_{2j}}(t) & \hat{r}_{n_2}(t) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \hat{c}_{n_{N1}}(t) & \dots & \hat{c}_{n_{Nj}}(t) & \hat{r}_{n_N}(t) \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where $\hat{c}_{n_{ij}}(t)$ represents the j th IMF of the i th white noise, and $\hat{r}_{n_i}(t)$ represents the residual mode of the i th white noise. $E_j(n_i(t))$ is defined as a set that includes the j th IMF of $n_i(t)$, $E_1(\hat{n}_i(t))$ is expressed as:

$$E_1(\hat{n}_i(t)) = (\hat{c}_{n_{i1}}(t) \hat{c}_{n_{i2}}(t) \dots \hat{c}_{n_{ij}}(t) \dots \hat{c}_{n_{iN}}(t))^T \quad (7)$$

6. Construct signal $X_{new_1}(t)$ and decompose it by EMD (only decompose the first IMF):

$$X_{new_1}(t) = \hat{r}_1(t) + E_1(\hat{n}_i(t)) \quad (8)$$

7. As in steps 3 and 4, obtain the second IMF $\hat{c}_2(t)$ and residual mode $\hat{r}_2(t)$ of the CEEMDAN.

8. Obtain $X_{new_{j-1}}(t)$ and repeat steps 6 and 7.

9. $x(t)$ is expressed as:

$$x(t) = \sum_{i=1}^L \hat{c}_i(t) + r(t) \quad (9)$$

where L represents the number of IMFs by the CEEMDAN, and $r(t)$ represents the residual mode.

Modified versions of the CEEMDAN have been recently proposed in [45].

Fig. 1. Overall diagram of the solving process.

2.3. Comparative analysis between FFT and HHT

One hundred years ago, Jean Baptiste Fourier showed that any waveform in the real world can be generated by adding up sine waves; this was valid for periodic signals. Later it was shown that the Fourier transform was able to work with non-periodic signals. The Fourier transform is probably the most widely applied signal processing tool in science and engineering. It reveals the frequency composition of a time series $x(t)$ by transforming it from the time domain into the frequency domain. The Fourier transform was undergoing modifications to improve its resolution and detection of harmonics, and this led to the FFT, which is an algorithm to calculate the discrete Fourier transform (DFT) more efficiently. A Fourier transform converts a signal in the time domain to the frequency domain (spectrum), and the DFT can convert a time-domain discrete signal into a frequency-domain discrete spectrum. Assume that we have a series of samples $x[n]$ for $0 \leq n \leq N$, then the DFT of the signal is a sequence $x[k]$ given by (10):

$$X[k] = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x[n] e^{-j2\pi nk/N}, \tag{10}$$

The FFT does not refer to a new type of Fourier transform. It refers to a more efficient algorithm for computing the DFT. The time taken to evaluate a DFT on a computer depends principally on the number of multiplications involved. DFT needs N^2 multiplications. FFT only needs $N \log_2(N)$. The DFT is rewriting in (11) and it is known as FFT:

$$X[k] = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x[n] W_N^{nk}, \tag{11}$$

where,

$$W_N = e^{-j2\pi/N} \text{ and } W_N^{nk} = e^{-j2\pi nk/N}$$

The main advantage of the HHT over FFT is the possibility to decompose signals without the need to assume stationary and linearity, and it generates both amplitude and frequency information as a function of time [46]. The FFT provides an efficient algorithm for converting data from the time domain into the frequency domain when the signals have some conditions that are not always easy to find in real systems. Different authors have carried out a comparative analysis between these two strategies [47,48]. In particular, the Fourier spectrum gives the most important frequency components of the electrical signals whereas the HHT, by means of the EMD technique, provides a more complete spectrum of frequencies [34]. The FFT produces some undesirable characteristics in spectrum analysis like aliasing and leakage whereas the HHT has the mode-mixing problem that does not allow differences in close frequencies.

2.4. Instantaneous frequency (IF) detection

The notion of IF has been previously explored in [2,49]. Since signals are not truly sinusoidal in practice, the concept of frequency must be analyzed in greater depth. Some research has been done on this subject. However, many aspects remain open for discussion. Generally, signals coming from the physical systems have been analyzed using the

Table 1

Key features of two households in Jaén (southern Spain).

	Household #1	Household #2
Total annual consumption (kWh/year)	2626	3033
Total surface (m2)	125	100
Number of family members	2	5
Is there at least one adult home during the morning?	No	No
Electric heating	No	No
Electric air condition	Yes	Yes
Building type	Semidetached house	Flat
Contracted power from the electric mains (kW)	2.30	3.45
Number of phases	1-phase	1-phase

Fourier transform, which gives time-invariant amplitude and frequency values. The inherited uncertainty principle associated with the Fourier transform makes the concept of an IF hard to define because the uncertainty principle is a consequence of the Fourier transform (or any other type of integral transform). Thus, if we do not apply an integral transform in the frequency computation, we would not be bounded by the uncertainty principle [41]. From a Fourier analysis point of view, the frequency of a signal would be derived from its time period, which is the time taken to complete one stationary time period. However, for a nonstationary waveform, the frequency would be hard to define. Another way to define the frequency is as the angular velocity that corresponds with the rate of change of its phase. If it is possible to define a unique phase for a signal, it will be possible to calculate its rate of change and thereby its frequency. The frequency obtained in this way is unique at any instant in time and is called IF. It is possible to define only one IF for a signal at any point in time [2,49]. This method has a problem with multi-component signals and therefore requires a pre-decomposition, where EMD can be called upon.

IF was computed from analytic signals through HT. The HT, however, deals poorly with multi-component signals. HHT estimates the instantaneous frequency and amplitude of a given signal. To do this, it first decomposes any signal down to mono-components called IMFs by using EMD. The function $x(t)$ is defined as

$$x(t) = r(t) + \sum c_i(t) = r(t) + \sum a_i(t) \cos(\theta_i(t)), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N. \tag{12}$$

where $c_i(t)$ is the IMF number i , $a_i(t)$ and $\theta_i(t)$ are instantaneous amplitude and phase, respectively, and N is the number of IMFs. The residual $r(t)$ is a monotone function. The instantaneous frequency $f_i(t)$ for each IMF $c_i(t)$ is defined by

$$f_i(t) \triangleq \frac{1}{2\pi} \cdot \frac{d\theta_i(t)}{dt}. \tag{13}$$

3. Results and discussion

This section shows how the decomposition using the techniques described in Section 2 detects the oscillation modes associated with household-consumption load profiles and reveals the importance of the data sampling frequency (temporal data granularity) for time-series.

Fig. 2. Data acquisition system in the households [19].

First, the EMD technique was applied, and subsequently the EEMD and CEEMDAN techniques were computed for comparison purposes. The IMFs obtained for different time scales as well as their IFs determine the oscillation modes and therefore the features of the consumption load profiles. Finally, the signal reconstruction under different techniques allows evaluating their accuracy as well as the influence analysis of data granularity.

Fig. 1 shows an overall diagram of the solving process. In this figure, the use of EMD technique is considered. Nevertheless, the structure is the same for the other techniques implemented.

The different techniques were implemented in MATLAB. A computer with an Intel® Core™ i7-9700F (8 cores), 3.0–4.7 GHz, and 48-GB DDR4 was used.

3.1. Study case description

The case study is focused on two real-world households in the city of Jaén in southern Spain. These two households have different consumption characteristics, i.e., variable behavior in terms of the relationship between maximum and base loads as well as load fluctuations. Also, structural differences in the households are considered, as shown in Table 1. Household #1 is a semi-detached house with only two inhabitants meanwhile household #2 is a family flat with three children. A more detailed description on the characteristics for both households can be found in [19].

The layout of the data acquisition system for collecting consumption load profile data is shown in Fig. 2 [19]. The SMs in the planned SCADA system sample consumption data at a comparatively high frequency for this purpose (2 Hz, i.e., a pair at every second). This sampling frequency almost complies with the upper value of frequency fluctuation for the consumption profiles (0.01–4 Hz). A detail description of the technical specification of the SMs meters is given in [50].

The city of Jaén has a Mediterranean climate with hot summers but extremely cold winters. For this reason, both households were equipped with air conditioning systems and with a heating system for the entire building by means of a gas boiler. The difference existed in the air conditioning system. While household #2 had a conventional system, household #1 was equipped with a two-split system (living room and master bedroom).

The different features of the active power profile in each household are shown in Figs. 3(a), 3(b), and 3(c) for the periods of 100 s, half an hour, and one day, respectively. For household #2, the maximum daily load peak occurred at 22:00:00 h with a 0.5-s granularity reading of 4.13 kW (Fig. 3(c)). However, the reading for the 30-min granularity dropped to 1.69 kW, which signified a decrease of 59.09%. As can be

observed, the consumption load for household #1 had a sequence of peaks throughout the day for the finest data granularity. These peaks were strongly attenuated for a 1-min data granularity (Fig. 3(b)), and much more reduced for the coarse data resolutions [19]. These repeated peaks were caused by the operation of the refrigerator. As an example, the 0.5-s reading at 23:49:53 h was 2.27 kW, after which it dropped to 0.95 kW (a 58.14% decrease) for the 30-min granularity (Fig. 3(c)).

3.2. Case study in household #1

This section presents the results of applying the techniques in Section 2 to the data of household #1 to provide a comprehensive analysis on the features of the consumption load profile, characterized by a nonlinear and nonstationary behavior. In particular, the techniques are applied in three time slices: 100 s, half an hour, and one day. These three-time windows guarantee the detection of the entire frequency spectrum for the consumption load profile.

3.2.1. Analysis for the 100-s time slice

In this section the original consumption load profile is firstly decomposed into several IMFs using the EMD technique. The result of this technique is a set of five IMFs and a residue, which are depicted in Fig. 4 using a 100 s time slice. Unlike other methods of signal analysis, the EMD technique allows for eliminating and isolating noises at all frequencies. This noise is concentrated in the first IMFs which corresponds to the highest frequencies. The mode mixing phenomenon is shown in Fig. 4 since it is possible to detect how different types of oscillations appear in the same level of decomposition. On the other hand, the periods (frequency⁻¹) detected in the consumption load profile are 2.76, 5.63, 34.34, 109.77, and 110.52 s. This issue is found in more detail in the first columns of Table 2.

The most serious consequence of the mode mixing phenomenon is the reduced accuracy of the technique in detecting frequencies and therefore the characterization of oscillation modes. To gather more information on the accuracy of the EMD technique, the result of the signal reconstruction from some selected IMFs is compared with that of the original signal, which is used as a reference. This assessment is carried out, based on a mean-squared-error (MSE) index [51]. In particular, this error is given by the following:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{Y}_i - Y_i)^2 \quad (14)$$

where n is the size of the data, \hat{Y} represents the reconstruction of the signal, and Y is the original signal.

Fig. 3. Active power consumption in monitored households for different data granularities and time slices: (a) 100 s, (b) half and hour, (c) one day.

Table 2
Frequencies of oscillation modes and statistics of the consumption load profile in household #1 for the first 100 s.

EMD+HT			EEMD+HT			CEEMDAN+HT		
f^{-1} [s]	P [dB]	S	f^{-1} [s]	P [dB]	S	f^{-1} [s]	P [dB]	S
2.76	7.60	0.912	2.18	3.15	0.922	2.27	2.94	0.908
5.63	10.64	0.856	3.57	3.38	0.874	3.85	3.65	0.868
34.34	13.33	0.800	7.14	5.17	0.830	11.13	8.17	0.826
109.77	18.91	0.759	16.83	8.48	0.792	34.35	11.00	0.780
110.52	10.86	0.758	51.56	10.00	0.761	108.25	19.00	0.754
			112.12	14.88	0.751	99.12	17.23	0.754
			-2462.30	32.49	0.749	-3802.74	42.18	0.749
			-6044.37	35.57	0.749			
			-9455.37	25.22	0.749			
			-9291.69	-0.65	0.749			

One of the most commonly used variables to characterize the behavior of an IMF is its entropy (S); entropy analysis has been recently introduced in [52,53]. When an IMF has a high entropy this implies a high randomness or uncertainty of the power demand in the consumption load profile. An alternative method to disclose and understand this phenomenon is to analyze the distribution of the IFs in Fig. 5. The box plot shows the trend of the power-demand behavior and the outliers found in the detection. Most of the outliers are due to the mode mixing phenomenon.

To decrease the effect of the mode mixing phenomenon, the same decomposition was carried out with two techniques of increasing complexity, i.e., the EEMD and CEEMDAN techniques. Comparing the three techniques, the EEMD technique found twice as many IMFs as the EMD

technique, and the CEEMDAN technique determined 40% more IMFs. Although the aforementioned matter was noticeably reduced, another issue was found: the edge effect. The extremes of decompositions (IMFs) presented more variations when applying the HT, which implies using Eq. (13). The precision of the HHT time–frequency analysis seriously suffers from the edge effect, especially when the data presents high randomly or the data length is short. This phenomenon is called the edge effect. This issue was present in the three techniques, but it was strengthened for the EEMD and CEEMDAN techniques. The edge effect can be observed in the right part of Fig. 4, specifically in IMF 5. This effect is the reason for negative frequencies generated in the frequency assessment found in the profile. This concern is shown in Table 2, and those frequencies are highlighted in bold font.

Fig. 4. IMFs and IP of the active power in household #1 using the EMD method.

Fig. 5. Distribution of IFs in household #1 for the 100 s time slice.

In order to compare the accuracy of above-mentioned techniques, the MSE index was evaluated. Although the EEMD and CEEMDAN techniques detected more oscillation modes, this research discarded some of them on the basis of their low energy content. Thus, the rows representing the frequencies underlined in gray were discarded in the reconstruction. Under this assumption, the EEMD technique just took into account the periods (frequency⁻¹) of 16.83, 51.56, and 112.12 s, meanwhile the CEEMDAN technique considered the periods of 11.13, 34.35, 108.25, and 99.12 s.

The MSE index by the three techniques is shown in Table 3. Although more frequencies were discarded in EEMD and CEEMDAN, against EMD, their MSEs were lower, which signaled a more accurate reconstruction. Conversely, the MSE in the EMD technique was very high. As can be observed, the CEEMDAN technique had a high level of accuracy. In fact, the more complex technique, the greater its accuracy was with the allowable variation in the computation time. Consequently, there was no increase in the computational burden.

Table 3

MSE index and associated computation time for different methods based on the signal reconstruction in household #1 for the first 100 s.

Technique	MSE [W ²]	Computation time [s]
<i>EMD+HT</i>	15696.921	0.127
<i>EEMD+HT</i>	9.342	0.967
<i>CEEMDAN+HT</i>	4.966	1.205

3.2.2. Analysis for the 30-min time slice

From the results, which cannot be included here in their entirety because of space limitations, in the HHT the mixture of modes is still present, and in the EEMD and CEEMDAN techniques the edge effect continues to be present. As expected, Table 4 shows a greater number of periods (frequency⁻¹) detected due to the larger time slice. In this time

Table 4

Frequencies of oscillation modes and statistics of the consumption load profile in household #1 for the first half an hour.

EMD+HT			EEMD+HT			CEEMDAN+HT		
f^{-1} [s]	P [dB]	S	f^{-1} [s]	P [dB]	S	f^{-1} [s]	P [dB]	S
8.27	27.49	0.929	3.34	25.49	0.901	3.38	25.02	0.888
8.09	24.25	0.785	3.63	24.59	0.822	10.88	26.85	0.823
13.95	24.67	0.666	6.72	21.03	0.734	11.73	24.51	0.728
98.30	22.54	0.558	12.51	15.20	0.675	17.37	20.46	0.656
190.30	21.03	0.479	19.34	9.67	0.613	29.37	15.29	0.576
288.55	25.89	0.453	40.58	8.92	0.555	63.38	13.37	0.510
844.06	28.57	0.443	89.79	9.95	0.500	189.95	17.83	0.462
			170.57	12.10	0.469	342.22	24.81	0.451
			286.73	16.28	0.457	870.86	28.97	0.443
			342.88	18.25	0.451	1706.91	24.45	0.440
			850.62	22.47	0.443	-25290697.28	45.50	0.437
			-172910.18	38.98	0.437			
			-780255.69	38.34	0.437			
			-969218.13	20.71	0.437			

Table 5

MSE index and associated computation time for different methods based on the signal reconstruction in household #1 for the first half an hour.

Technique	MSE [W^2]	Computation time [s]
EMD+HT	37768.057	1.720
EEMD+HT	8.031	9.281
CEEMDAN+HT	0.000	9.463

slice, only one frequency was discarded (40.58 s) for the EEMD technique and three negative frequencies were caused by the edge effect. In the CEEMDAN technique, no frequency was ruled out and only one negative frequency was found. It is also important to emphasize that the result of this time slice was more accurate since more frequencies were detected with a higher energy component and, according to the IMF, lower entropy. Obviously, the higher period detection was due to the longer time slice. In particular, the first technique (EMD) produced 7 IMFs. EEMD detected twice the frequencies, and the CEEMDAN found 57% more frequencies with respect to EMD.

Despite increasing the time slice, the error in the signal reconstruction by using the EEMD and CEEMDAN techniques was reduced from detected oscillation modes. Contrary for the EMD technique, the MSE increased by 2.4 times with respect to the 100-s time slice. In the other techniques, the error for EEMD was reduced by 14% and 0% for the CEEMDAN (Table 5). Computation time obviously increased for this longer time slice, but the time relationship between the different techniques remained stable.

3.2.3. Analysis for the one-day time slice

The analysis of the 1-day time slice was a challenging task because it contains the greatest wealth of oscillatory modes. This includes the behavior of the inhabitants of the household throughout the day, including all the electrical appliances that can generate oscillation modes for the specific period of one day. However, this wider analysis reveals the most details on load profile features. Due to the longer time slice, the methods can detect more frequencies, see Table 6. Again, from results not shown in graphs, the problem of mode mixing and the edge effect is still present but with greater relevance in the first IMFs.

On the basis of the results shown in Table 6, the EEMD and CEEMDAN techniques found more frequencies than the EMD technique. In this time slice, 3.4 times more frequencies for EEMD were detected and 2.8 times more frequencies for CEEMDAN. The edge effect was 60% more intrusive in EEMD with respect to the CEEMDAN by finding more negative frequencies.

None of the detected frequencies were discarded since all of them had an acceptable energy level. The level of entropy was inversely proportional to the number of IMFs, i.e., the first frequencies detected had a high level of entropy. This means that the power demand behavior should not be taken with certainty. In contrast, the latter frequencies

had a low entropy, which means that their behavior was less random. The HHT frequency range was much larger than the one found by using the FFT [19]. This means that the active power signal was both nonlinear and nonstationary.

Fig. 6 depicts a 1-day sequence of frequencies corresponding to the time domain using the CEEMDAN technique of the original signal shown in Fig. 3(c). It reveals 28 periods, where the fluctuation of active power can be inferred. These IMFs are organized into a decreasing frequency order due to the higher number of temporal oscillations of the signal, with respect to each successive iteration.

The technique based on the EMD, EEMD and CEEMDAN allows establishing relationships between the frequencies of oscillation modes and their sources based on specific residential electrical appliances. According to household #1, it was possible to deduce that the behavior of the first IMFs was due to high-frequency switching from the power electronics of the modern equipment. Additionally, the first oscillations showed consumption peaks of large electrical appliances, e.g., dishwasher, washing machine, electric water heater, and dryer. The IMFs 13 to 17 show the behavior of highly variable loads (e.g., LED, florescent and halogen lamps, smart phones, tablets, BlueRay-DVD players). IMF 28 represents the general behavior of household #1, i.e., a base consumption is maintained during most of the day, but when 17:00 arrives, consumption begins to increase. This behavior is generally provided upon the arrival of its inhabitants to the household.

The error assessment for the three different techniques was similar to previous time slices (Table 7). The CEEMDAN technique has demonstrated a high accuracy and an admissible computation time in relation to the EMD technique. Finally, Fig. 7 shows the signal reconstruction for the half hour and one day analysis, with the HHT variants, i.e., the EEMD and CEEMDAN techniques. In this figure, the accuracy of these methods can be evidenced, since a small error is observed in Figs. 7(a) and 7(c), meanwhile Figs. 7(b) and 7(d) underline an error of 0, as shown in Tables 5 and 7.

3.3. Case of study in household #2

In household #2, the same techniques were applied. Upon initial inspection, equivalent results can be inferred and therefore this section underlines the main differences in both households for the one-day time slice under the all mentioned techniques. The greatest difference is found in the number of periods detected. Although, it is evident in Fig. 3(b) that this household has greater oscillations, the results do not always show this to an adequate extent. Thus, the result obtained for the EMD+HT was different than household #1 since 7 IMFs were obtained with a very high error in the reconstruction. The second difference came from the analysis with the EEMD method, which provided 35 IMFs, one IMF more than household #1, and an error nine times greater. The third difference was the number of periods detected with the CEEMDAN method, where 26 IMFs were detected.

Table 6
Frequencies of oscillation modes and statistics of the consumption load profile in household #1 for one day.

EMD+HT			EEMD+HT			CEEMDAN+HT		
f^{-1} [s]	P [dB]	S	f^{-1} [s]	P [dB]	S	f^{-1} [s]	P [dB]	S
4.90	26.71	0.949	2.11	19.84	0.945	2.88	19.13	0.962
5.06	24.85	0.805	2.52	14.25	0.909	2.87	17.89	0.908
15.85	26.17	0.675	3.55	11.33	0.834	4.23	17.52	0.837
64.34	28.09	0.548	5.05	10.78	0.790	6.50	17.73	0.768
200.07	28.82	0.420	7.19	10.50	0.744	10.34	18.87	0.704
432.18	29.88	0.333	10.21	11.67	0.697	16.46	22.17	0.638
800.61	29.92	0.294	14.71	10.62	0.652	26.63	21.80	0.582
1880.58	37.19	0.284	20.61	10.21	0.607	45.05	18.18	0.533
5414.77	40.11	0.281	29.15	10.86	0.564	71.12	19.01	0.481
14509.37	37.26	0.280	40.60	10.36	0.527	107.34	21.46	0.432
			55.78	11.98	0.494	135.64	19.80	0.396
			75.01	12.95	0.468	166.84	21.43	0.374
			97.42	13.18	0.444	178.85	22.91	0.363
			131.74	14.10	0.420	211.29	23.43	0.356
			171.12	13.42	0.398	232.92	22.52	0.346
			238.12	15.71	0.372	273.48	21.78	0.336
			316.62	15.56	0.351	315.41	23.96	0.326
			482.75	16.50	0.330	400.08	23.27	0.316
			864.48	18.21	0.309	469.75	23.23	0.301
			1373.16	20.05	0.298	645.09	30.18	0.291
			2218.37	21.81	0.287	1184.61	33.50	0.287
			3928.23	24.14	0.287	2711.03	46.30	0.284
			5078.68	25.49	0.285	4331.55	43.28	0.281
			6184.23	24.87	0.282	7890.29	42.10	0.281
			10857.34	30.00	0.281	17451.69	42.48	0.280
			90957.16	32.08	0.280	29283.71	40.07	0.280
			77076.63	31.97	0.280	44290.64	36.66	0.280
			43758.04	30.98	0.280	-2428289.94	48.12	0.280
			-2059780.13	29.25	0.280			
			90659.07	26.47	0.280			
			-1959835.83	27.71	0.280			
			-2257876.81	33.15	0.280			
			-3353298.76	26.80	0.280			
			-2561329.87	14.00	0.280			

Table 7
MSE index and associated computation time of different methods based on the signal reconstruction in household #1 for a day.

Technique	MSE [W^2]	Computation time [s]
EMD+HT	57408.427	308.026
EEMD+HT	15.775	1662.087
CEEMDAN+HT	0.000	1809.682

That is two periods less than household #1. In both reconstructions, the error was null. By evaluating the results and taking into account the specific behavior of some loads in this house, the following oscillation modes were accurately detected: IMF 18 with a period for demand of 13 min and 27 s, IMF 19 with an oscillation every 22 min and 53 s, IMF 21 with a period of 1 h, 8 min and 42 s, and finally IMF 25 with a period of 3 h, 1 min and 7 s. The relationship raised between the elements of the power electronics and the periods detected are based on a comparison with [19]. More oscillation modes were generated by the fact that household #2 included more inhabitants and had a more intense electricity consumption, which originated a richer transitory behavior. In contrast, household #1 had electrical appliances with higher consumption but more stable.

3.4. Influence of temporal data granularity for specifying consumption load profiles

This section focuses on the influence analysis of temporal data granularity for describing the features of the household-consumption load profiles. To this aim, the signal reconstruction for both households was carried out from the most accurate technique in Section 2, i.e., CEEMDAN. This technique was applied by discarding oscillation modes of decreasing frequencies, as shown in Table 8. This permitted

coarse-grained data be computed. The analysis included three time slices (100 s, 0.5 h, and one day).

Table 8 only summarizes the results of reconstruction procedure for the longest time slice evaluated in the previous section, i.e. one day. Four study cases were planned for discarding the oscillation modes of time periods less than 30 s, 1 min, 5 min, and 10 min.

The information loss of the profile features for coarse-grained data was evaluated using two error indexes, i.e., a power comparison index P and an amplitude comparison index A . They are defined as follows: $P = (P_R/P_S) \cdot 100\%$ and $A = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n (R_{1j}/X_{1j}) \cdot 100\%$, where P_R is the power of the reconstructed signal, P_S the power of the original signal, R_{1j} is the reconstructed signal, X_{1j} is the original signal, and n is the size of the data. Therefore, P represents the ratio of power of the reconstructed signal to the original signal meanwhile A represents the ratio of amplitude.

For both households, the maximum error when discarding oscillation modes of a time period lower than 1 min was limited up to 0.69%. This means that a very accurate description of the profile can be obtained for intermediate data-resolution of up to 1 min. For the readings of 5- and 10-min granularity, the error only increased up to 1.89% and 2.52%, respectively, in household #1. However, the accuracy of the description of the profile strongly decreased in household #2. The increase in errors with 5- and 10-min coarser granularity was greater than in household #1 and achieved 6.61% and 9.56%, respectively. This lack of accuracy indicates the need to adjust the data granularity at least at 1 min. Results underlined how the oscillations of a low period (high frequency) were more relevant in household #2, showing greater errors due to a more pulsating behavior from consumers' habits by using the electrical appliances. Although household #1 included more oscillation modes, these were of smaller amplitude, being less relevant these low-frequency oscillations. This approach highlights the information loss regarding the profile features for coarse-grained data.

Fig. 6. Decomposition of the active power using the CEEMDAN technique.

It is important to highlight that the previous analysis was repeated on different analysis windows of 100 s, 0.5 h in a day, and on different 24-hour analysis windows in a month. Since similar results were found for corresponding cases, it can be concluded that results shown in Table 8 are representative for different days of a month.

Fig. 8 represents the IF (vertical axis) versus time (horizontal axis), while the instantaneous amplitude corresponding to each time is color-coded. As there is an instantaneous amplitude–frequency pair at every second the total number of points (pairs) in the full-scale graph is quite high ($N = 172800$). Therefore, the figure is easier to understand if the

Fig. 7. Reconstructed active power signal in household #1 for different time slices under several techniques: (a) EEMD with 30-min time slice; (b) CEEMDAN with 30-min time slice; (c) EEMD with 1-day time slice; (d) CEEMDAN with 1-day time slice.

Table 8

Error in the signal reconstruction by using the CEEMDAN method for different data granularity.

Error in CEEMDAN				
Periods	Household #1		Household #2	
	P [%]	A [%]	P [%]	A [%]
T > 30 s	99.50	99.48	99.47	99.29
T > 1 min	99.26	99.31	99.23	98.98
T > 5 min	98.14	98.11	92.39	92.72
T > 10 min	97.53	97.48	90.84	90.44

pairs are drawn as scattered points, that is, not forming a line. This graph helps us to understand the main differences in the behavior of the power demand in both households. Household #1 showed a more uniform consumption pattern throughout the day with the characteristics of mixed frequencies at every moment. On the other hand, household #2 concentrated the variability of the consumption around 16:00. Harmonics appear as vertical lines but with more relevant frequencies (dark red in Figs. 8(a) and 8(c)).

The representation of the power-demand frequency shows a fairly stationary behavior at high frequencies, although random peaks can be noticed at different times of the day. Various harmonics can be clearly identified in the spectrum, especially in Fig. 8(a) between 0.5 and 0.8 Hz. The comparison of Figs. 8(b) and 8(d) discloses great differences between both households, i.e., household #2 has more oscillation modes that are nonstationary in the intermediate range of frequencies, between 0.002 Hz (8.33 min) and 0.01 Hz (100 s).

4. Conclusions

This paper has proposed a methodology to analyze the features of the household-consumption load profiles based on signal analysis. Three techniques were planned: EMD, EEMD and CEEMDAN. The best accuracy was achieved with CEEMDAN, although the other techniques also shown a great potential in its application. The methodology is

based on the decomposition of the original signal into frequency bands, and then the IF is computed allowing different oscillations be identified in time and frequency domain. Furthermore, to wider the abilities of the methodology, the Hilbert spectrum was included to identify frequency variations in the time domain. Through this study, it has become clear that the spectral analysis of household consumption load data and their oscillatory modes is a challenging task

The EMD technique has multiple applications in different fields and has provided suitable results in literature. However, the mode mixing problem is evident in EMD when the signal under analysis has multiple harmonics. One solution to this concern is the use of the EEMD and CEEMDAN techniques. After reviewing the literature, it was found that these techniques have not yet been studied in depth because of their computationally high cost. In this paper, these techniques made it possible to observe the different oscillation modes of a signal in a clearer way, and the detection of IFs was also more evident.

The comparison of the EMD, EEMD, and CEEMDAN techniques underlined how the mode mixing phenomenon and the edge effect can be reduced; this is clear when observing IMFs. From the result of the CEEMDAN technique, it is possible to clearly identify the variation in the time domain of the oscillation modes, especially at low frequencies, which are not easy to detect with traditional methods. All the techniques presented have shown good performance for different applications, and this is something that should be highlighted. For example, in this study, the CEEMDAN technique achieved the best accuracy because of the multiple oscillation modes generated in the consumption load profiles analyzed, but this entailed an attainable computational burden in relation to the other techniques. In other applications with signals including fewer oscillations, suitable accuracy was achieved with the EMD technique with a much lower computational cost.

A good selection of IMFs allows having a new signal without noise and with the main frequency components. In some cases, it will be necessary to establish classification thresholds to select the IMFs using parameters, such as energy, standard deviation, or entropy; in our study, accurate results were obtained taking into account only the entropy. The accuracy of the reconstruction method was validated by

Fig. 8. HHT for the consumption load (detail for a 1-day period) with a rate of two samples per second. (a) Hilbert–Huang Spectrum for household #1 (contains all IMFs); (b) Discrete Hilbert–Huang Spectrum for household #1; (c) Hilbert–Huang Spectrum for household #2 (contains all IMFs); (d) Discrete Hilbert–Huang Spectrum for household #2.

comparing the power and amplitude of the original signal and the new signal obtained from selected IMFs. This validates that no relevant information is lost in this process and the main oscillation modes that characterize the load profile features were identified.

The overall influence that temporal data granularity had on the description of features of the household-consumption load profiles was also performed in this study. Results showed that some important loads (e.g., cooling or heating devices, electric water heaters, etc.) produced oscillations that became increasingly ill-suited for resolutions of 1 min or higher. This confirms that coarse granularities should not be used to collect consumption data because they do not reflect the reality. Nonetheless, the accuracy of these features was found to largely depend on the load profile analyzed. For the first time, this paper has proposed indicators whose evaluation has allowed quantifying the loss of information associated with coarse granularity data. Thus, in household #1, a very accurate reconstruction (error < 2.52%) was obtained with coarse-grained data up to 10 min. In any case, an intermediate data-resolution of 30 s showed feature characterization closer to those of 0.5 s since errors were limited to 0.71%.

Future work in the field should take the current limitation of this study into consideration. Further analysis could be conducted with other households of different characteristics, or the methodology could be applied to a large set of buildings.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Mauricio Sanabria-Villamizar: Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Software, Data curation, Validation, Writing – original draft. **Maximiliano Bueno-López:** Conceptualization, Validation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Preparation. **Jesus C. Hernández:** Conceptualization, Validation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Project administration, Investigation, Resources, Software, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Project administration. **David Vera:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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